

Report on Animal Welfare Principles

Deliverable 8.1 (WP8)

Summary report on the animal welfare principles applied by INFRAFRONTIER and the IMPC

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The IPAD-MD project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 653961

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The INFRAFRONTIER and the IMPC consortia are strongly committed to the implementation of the 3R principle (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement), in the strict compliance with animal experimentation regulation and in the promotion of animal welfare recommendations, both among the members of the scientific community and in the society, in general.

The replacement of animal models has been promoted thanks to the impressive accumulation of genomic data information from many different species, hence allowing addressing in silico experiments which, before, had to be addressed using live animals.

The reduction and refinement of animal models have been promoted through the entire execution of the IPAD-MD Project, at all its corresponding meetings and workshops, owing to the fact that new and optimized technologies have been made available to mouse embryology researchers (including genome editing tools, such as CRISPR-Cas9 reagents) and, most importantly, thanks to the evolution of mouse cryopreservation and assisted-reproductive biology techniques. In this regard, the existence today of more than 7300 mouse lines cryopreserved in all different EMMA-INFRAFRONTIER nodes, and the 500 requests that are regularly dispatched annually has permitted saving a significant number of animals that would have been used otherwise.

The promotion of the 3R concept and the strategies developed for optimizing the use of animals in biomedicine within the INFRAFRONTIER consortium has been present at all IPAD-MD meetings held during the entire life of the project, including the INFRAFRONTIER-IPAD-MD conferences organized in

Munich (Germany, July 2015, June 2016), Athens (Greece, November 2017), Brussels (Belgium, June 2018), Madrid (Spain, November 2019), and in many other conferences, courses, congresses, symposiums and workshops, such as the mouse genetics courses at Institut Pasteur Montevideo (Uruguay, September 2015, October 2019), the mouse genome editing courses at IMG and CCP/BioCEV (Prague, Czech Republic, March 2016, April 2017, April 2018) seminar delivered at CARD institute, University of Kumamoto (Japan, November 2015), EMMA mouse cryopreservation course at CNR-Monterotondo (November 2015) and at Institut Pasteur (Paris, France, October 2016), at the Ramon Areces foundation (Madrid, Spain, November 2016), at the annual meeting of the International Embryo Transfer Society (Austin, TX, USA, January 2017), at the Mouse Phenomim genetics courses (Strasbourg, France, June 2017 and May 2019), at a mouse genetic and breeding course at Roslin Institute (Edinburg, Scotland, UK, June 2016), at the Animal Welfare Athens Institut Pasteur course (Greece, June 2017), at the diverse genome editing courses organized by CNB-CSIC in collaboration with CIBERER-ISCI in Madrid (Spain), in 2017, 2018 and 2019, at the Congento consortium meeting in Oeiras (Portugal, October 2018) and the animal research transparency meeting in Strasbourg (France, October 2018), at the PATHBIO kick-off meeting in Barcelona (Spain, March 2019), at the CECs Research Centre in Valdivia (Chile, October 2019), at the Mouse Transgenesis and Genome Edition course at the University of Adelaide (Australia, October 2019) and the transparency meeting in animal research at University of Helsinki (Finland, November 2019).

It is worth noting that the activities on promoting animal welfare and the adequate knowledge on animal experimentation launched from Spain where the CNB-CSIC, under the leadership of Dr. Lluís Montoliu, responsible for this WP8 work package as well, has been contributing extensively. In particular, the Spanish Agreement on Transparency in Animal Research was launched in

September 2016 and, today, more than 140 institutions from all over Spain have adhered to the four simple and basic principles committing signing institutions to: (1) speak with clarity on when, how and why we use animals in research; (2) provide adequate information to mass media and lay public on the conditions in which we do research projects that require the use of animals and about the results we derive from them; (3) promote initiatives to generate a better knowledge and understanding in the society on the use of animals in research; and (4) inform annually on the progress of the agreement and sharing experiences. The Spanish transparency agreement has been audited annually by the European Association of Research Animals (EARA). All information can be obtained from:

<http://wwwuser.cnb.csic.es/~montoliu/transparencia/transparencia.html>

This transparency agreement in Spain has been extremely well received by the Society and mass media and numerous articles in the press, commentaries in radios and programs in TV have been broadcasted. In addition, several initiatives using video have been launched from Spain concerning the dissemination of examples of good and responsible use of animals in biomedicine research, including efforts towards our understanding and eventual development of treatments of human rare diseases. Diverse examples are available from the transparency agreement web page in Spain:

<http://wwwuser.cnb.csic.es/~montoliu/transparencia/transparencia.html>

These four principles were imported and adapted from the equivalent initiative launched in UK in 2014 on the Concordate on Openness on Animal Research, currently extended to more than 122 British institutions committed to share their efforts on animal welfare and to explain their use of animals in their research projects. To date, only UK and Spain have deployed and successfully completed such transparency initiatives. Thanks to the IPAD-MD project we have

been campaigning for the transparency in animal research in Portugal, France, Germany, Finland, Denmark, Italy, Netherlands and Belgium and it is likely that some of these countries will soon launch similar initiatives, particularly Portugal and Belgium.

In summary, through the continuous consideration of the implications for animal welfare, whenever novel strategies, solutions or technologies involving research on animals are being developed, at all activities promoted and/or organized from IPAD-MD we have been accomplishing and disseminating the results of the original objectives of this work package:

1. Ensure that animal welfare is adequately taken into consideration throughout the IPAD-MD project.
2. Provide input and recommendations to the IPAD-MD topics and to the other work packages (WP3-7)
3. Summarise the INFRAFRONTIER and IMPC animal welfare principles for the communication to the international stakeholders, the wider scientific community and the general public.